

WHEEL OF COMPETENCIES: INDUSTRY DEMANDS OF COMPETENCIES FOR RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

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ABSTRACT

On the basis of the current state of research, this study identifies and validates future-oriented competencies. Using quantitative social research methods, it then investigates demands in industry. This involved, first, an evaluation of literature and the identification of competencies for research and innovation (R&I) activities. Next, from clusters of the identified competencies I derived 14 different types. On this basis, I generated a competency profile that informs the development of a tool for R&I, the *Wheel of Competencies*. With this newly developed tool specific competency profiles can be generated and analysed.

Second, I operationalized and implemented the competence components in a questionnaire. On this basis, 200 CEOs and heads of research and development (R&D) departments of medium-sized and large enterprises in Germany were surveyed in November and December 2021 using computer-assisted telephone interviews (CATI). All enterprises have at least 50 employees and an in-house R&D department. In addition, enterprises have to belong to one of the following industry sectors: automotive, chemical, electrical or mechanical engineering.

The results show that certain competencies are in very high demand across all industries, while others are more specific to an industry sector. Overall, the results indicate that the competencies in demand address the dynamic complexity in collaborative R&I processes. The results presented here make an important evidence-based contribution to curriculum development in engineering education based on future-oriented competencies and illustrates which transfer activities and collaborative formats are increasingly relevant.

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1 INTRODUCTION

To conceptualize Research and Innovation (R&I) activities, the quadruple-helix model is the state of the art to understand the generation and impact of academic knowledge [1]. It explains how collaborations between the sectors academia, industry, politics and society enable sustainable innovations that can drive socio-technical transformations [2].

A means to this end is Knowledge and Technology Transfer (KTT). Here, KTT is not understood as transfer in the sense of its Latin origin from *transferre*, but as exchange and joint generation of knowledge, i.e. a broader understanding.

This generation of knowledge is described as inter- and transdisciplinary as well as application-oriented, so-called mode 2, and is characterized by being "socially accountable and reflexive" [3]. Such knowledge provides answers to grand societal challenges and 'wicked problems', because it takes into account their complexity and systemic nature, and also because solutions are developed jointly by actors from different sectors. Currently, this is being discussed under the term 'new mission-orientation', in which politically negotiated missions divide complex challenges into manageable problems [4]. An example of this are the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that in turn inform research policies such as EU's Horizon Europe framework program.

However, to collaboratively generate new knowledge and find future-oriented solutions to pressing challenges is no easy task. It makes certain demands of those involved. In particular, activities in innovation ecosystems, i.e. collaborating stakeholders from academia, industry, politics, and society, require competencies and skills that go beyond domain-specific knowledge and abilities. Such competencies are complementary to disciplinary hard skills and socio-communicative soft skills. Which competencies and skills will become more important in the future is the subject of various debates that are conducted under the labels 'professional skills', 'future skills', 'transversal or general skills', 'transfer skills', 'future-oriented competencies' and 'emerging skills'.

This study pursues two goals:

- First, it explores the question which (professional) competencies should be developed by actors in R&I collaborations, and,
- second, it seeks to validate a profile of such competencies by industry.

To this end, I first reviewed the state of research to identify relevant competencies for R&I activities and KTT in the literature. In a second step, the results were analysed, typologised, and transferred into a tool. These results were then, in a third step, validated in a quantitative survey of 200 medium-sized and large enterprises. The results complement our understanding of practice-oriented competencies and is relevant for curriculum development in engineering education.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 State of Research, Typology and Tool Development

Which competencies will become (more) relevant for collaborative R&I activities in the future (within the German innovation landscape) is the subject of various specialized discourses. My work is based on a broad concept of transfer, i.e. the concept of KTT referring to a dynamic process of generating knowledge in mission-oriented research collaborations [5]. I claim that pertaining to this understanding, works from the fields of transformative sciences, transdisciplinarity, education for sustainable development, key competencies, (future-, professional-, emerging-, 21st century-) skills are relevant. For each of these fields, I surveyed contemporary literature, and evaluated the state of research with a special focus on key literature and mission statements by national academies and advisory bodies, such as German Academy of Science and Engineering, German Advisory Council on Global Change, and Donors' Association for the Promotion of Humanities and Sciences in Germany. To this end, I identified professional skills and competencies for innovation activities.²

I build on Weinert's conception of competency [6]. Thus, competencies are more than knowledge and its application. It is a knowledge-based disposition to meet complex demands by drawing on and mobilizing psycho-social resources in varying contexts to solve a given problem [7,8].³ On this basis, I created a pool of all competencies relevant to R&I and KTT that are not strictly disciplinary, e.g. engineering mathematics like applied analysis. Next, as illustrated by α in Figure 2, I clustered the surveyed competencies and, following Kluge, developed fourteen types that are characterised by internal homogeneity and external heterogeneity [10]. For each type a definition was derived based on concepts in literature:

Table 1 - Competencies for R&I and KTT

1	<i>Agility</i> characterizes individuals who can adapt their behaviour and expectations as well as processes and structures flexibly and promptly to new framework conditions. They can react proactively, anticipatively, and proactively to changes by utilizing distributed knowledge and by continuously adapting to varying (social) situations [11,12].
2	<i>Agency in systems</i> refers to the ability to plan and realize actions and processes within complex personal, social and technical systems. The necessary prerequisites for this are the recognition and understanding of interdependencies between elements or parts of the system as well its boundaries. Specifically, this describes the ability to consider one's own actions

² I describe my methodology in more detail in 'Innovation Emloyability' (forthcoming).

³ In Chomsky's sense, I understand dispositions as the components of a competence that are expressed in observable actions [9]. Unlike Chomsky, however, I do not assume that these dispositions are essentially fixed but rather that they may be developed.

	in a larger context in order to identify necessities and assess potential consequences [13].
3	<i>Handling complexity</i> describes the ability to recognize and understand relevant relationships and patterns in situations with an unknown multitude of factors that interact dynamically. On that basis one's own actions and behaviour can then be adjusted accordingly [14–16].
4	<i>Process analysis and design</i> describes the ability to recognize opportunities and obstacles to achieving personal or professional objectives. It includes identifying limits of the scope of action, deriving steps for an effective and purposeful intervention, and managing processes [13,17,18].
5	<i>Teamwork</i> is the ability to work with others from different backgrounds, organizations, and disciplines. Working in teams requires building trust and communicating effectively face to face as well as using media services [13,19].
6	<i>Attitude towards challenges</i> describes the mindset that individuals exhibit towards cognitively demanding tasks and situations with no apparent strategy for dealing with them. Specifically, this refers to whether situations and tasks that are perceived as challenging tend to be avoided or whether they are seen as an opportunity to learn or try something new [20].
7	<i>Acting according to ethical principles</i> refers to knowledge and understanding of ethical positions including the ability to identify relevant ethical questions. It, then, refers to the ability to act in accordance with such ethical principles in order to realize an individual or societal value by considering ethical dimensions of conditions of application, norms, interests, and consequences. Specifically, this competency describes the ability to recognize and evaluate values and norms and to direct one's own actions toward values and norms, taking into account the respective context, and to be able to justify a chosen course of action [21–23].
8	<i>Agency despite uncertainties and contradictions</i> refers to the ability to recognize and understand ambiguity and heterogeneity, as well as to be able to set priorities independently in situations in which feelings of uncertainty or excessive demands arise, and to align one's own actions accordingly. Specifically, such agency describes the ability to assess situations with contradictory or unclear information and to prioritize information in order to direct personal or professional actions towards a given objective [13,14].
9	<i>Motivation to learn</i> describes the individual attitude toward acquiring new or deepening existing knowledge, skills or attitudes. The focus is on the willingness to control one's own learning process and to activate the necessary resources and social processes. Specifically, motivation to learn refers to the individual willingness to intentionally acquire new knowledge or skills and to develop one's existing portfolio which can also mean that an initiative is undertaken to create the prerequisites for doing so [13,24,25].

10	<i>Critical thinking</i> describes the ability to (reasonably) assess facts on the basis of their essential components against the background of given sources and possible alternatives by applying general standards of rationality. Critical thinking involves questioning and evaluating what is supposedly self-evident [26].
11	<i>Recognizing emotions and taking other perspectives</i> is the ability to perceive and assess emotions both in oneself and in others. Within a professional context it refers to management and control of emotions on the basis of different behaviours and incentives. This also includes the ability to place oneself in the shoes of other people or organizations. In practical terms, this involves assessing emotional states or attitudes of others and considering them when addressing these others [27–29].
12	<i>Reflection of own actions</i> describes the willingness and ability to critically analyse oneself along with personal actions. It includes the ability to manage the utilization of personal resources. In addition, it includes the ability to recognize and relate to underlying systems of behaviour, thinking and values. By extension, the ability to reflect also includes actions of other people. Practically, this describes the ability to contextualize actions by recognizing and evaluating the relevant influencing parameters. The opposite is routine action or acting according to instructions [30,31].
13	<i>Handling diversity</i> refers to an appreciative approach to diversity and the ability to recognize commonalities in professional, cultural, or personal diversity (e.g., goals or values) that form the basis for joint action in a communicative-social process. This involves the ability to direct diverse impulses towards a common objective by fostering commonality in a sensitive process of exchange and communication [19,32,33].
14	<i>Creativity</i> is the ability to generate, shape, and implement ideas in order to find unconventional, novel, and appropriate solutions to a given challenge. Creativity allows to generate original solutions to emerging, complex, and unconventional challenges. Finding such solutions requires an open-mindedness toward unconventional methods and approaches as well as the ability to develop ideas exploratorily [11,25].

Illustrated by β in Figure 2, I then developed the *Wheel of Competencies* from these fourteen competencies. It is a tool to illustrate competency profile for collaborative R&I activities and KTT formats in the context of the new mission orientation:

Fig. 1: Wheel of Competencies for Collaborative Research and Innovation

As a tool, the *Wheel of Competencies* may be used to compare different profiles, to identify potentials and to develop tailor-made training offers and teaching formats. Thus, it provides support for educators in engineering education to come to an understanding about desired results and outcomes of curriculum development processes. In order to validate the results and to survey such profiles, I subsequently conducted a quantitative study.

2.2 Survey

The study was designed as a quantitative survey of industry needs. Its intended to, first, validate the competencies and, second, to substantiate profiles that are needed by industry to collaborate in R&I. The survey was conducted in the form of structured computer-assisted telephone interviews [34]. In the fourth quarter of 2021, 200 managing directors or heads of R&D departments of medium-sized and large enterprises from the four largest industry sectors automotive engineering, electrical engineering, chemical engineering and mechanical engineering sectors were surveyed [35]. For each industry sector, I calculated the weighted values according to the relative size of the industry sector and size of the company in order to create a representative and accurate set of data to include in the analysis. In total, I was able to realize the following cases:

Table 2. Sample by industry sector and size of the company

Industry sector	Staff headcount 50-249	Staff headcount ≥250
Automotive engineering	31	16
Chemical engineering	31	16
Electrical engineering	34	22
Mechanical engineering	30	20

For the purpose of the present study, I operationalized the 14 competencies and converted these into questionnaire items with a 5-point Likert scale (γ). Each item inquired: “How relevant are the following factors for your company among your R&D employees: very relevant (=1), relevant (=2), neither relevant nor irrelevant (=3), rather irrelevant (=4) or not relevant at all (=5)?” Incomplete answers were excluded. For research pragmatic reasons, the questionnaire was limited to two items for each competency. Every item covers an essential part of each definition given in Table 1. I used validated items from empirical research and, if necessary, adjusted the wording of individual items [36]. Before the start of the study, I conducted a pretest, then conducted the semi-structured interviews (δ). In order to analyse and interpret the data gathered, I used the software PSPP for analysis of statistical data. For the visualization I utilized Microsoft Excel (ϵ).

Figure 2 - Research Process

For the analysis, all data were considered that were coherent with regard to a competency. To achieve coherence, those items were excluded that varied on a 5-point Likert scale with a value larger than 1 in regard to a single competency, i.e.

Δ (item a; item b) >1 . For example, the answer to Item 1 is “very relevant” (=1) and the answer to Item 2 is “rather irrelevant” (=4) on a 5-point Likert scale. Thus, a delta follows that is $4-1=3>1$. Because it is larger than 1, the answers were disregarded on the assumption that here “very relevant” and “rather irrelevant” are not coherent in respect to the competency in question. Applying this rule, the average number of cases considered per competency is 170 with a standard deviation of 19.28 among all fourteen competencies. The maximum is $n=194$ for *handling complexity* and the minimum is $n=122$ for *teamwork*.

While the *Wheel of Competency* as illustrated in Figure 3 is descriptive in regard to the relevance of the fourteen competencies, an ANOVA was conducted for the internal differentiation by competency and industry sectors.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Competencies for Research and Innovation

The results of the survey of R&D enterprises in engineering professions confirm in principle the competencies derived from literature. Figure 1 illustrates these findings. As this is a typologised summary of the latest research and debates, the data can essentially be interpreted as validation. However, the results also show that the relevance of individual competencies for collaborative R&D varies among competencies as well as among industry sectors.

Fig. 3. *Wheel of Competencies with adjusted values for all competencies (scale 1-3)*

Initially, when evaluating the data collected for all industry sectors, it shows that the enterprises rank the importance of the competencies surveyed as at least “rather

important" on average. With one exception, they have a mean value of <2 which translates into something between "rather important" and "very important". It is noticeable that *dealing with diversity*, *emotional competence* and, to a lesser extent, *creativity* rank behind the other competencies. Notably, *dealing with diversity* is the only competency with a value >2. The interviewed managers find it less important that their employees have these competencies. It is also striking that *agility* is less in demand than its presence in the discourse on forward-looking and innovative forms of work - particularly in the area of R&I - would lead one to expect [37].

Table 3. Competencies listed by mean value (possible max. = 1, min. = 5)

Competency	Mean value
motivation to learn	1,32
handling complexity	1,36
teamwork	1,41
process analysis and design	1,42
reflection of own actions	1,44
critical thinking	1,48
agency despite uncertainties and contradictions	1,49
acting according to ethical principles	1,52
agency in systems	1,53
agility	1,62
attitude towards challenges	1,63
creativity	1,77
recognizing emotions and taking other perspectives	1,85
handling diversity	2,10

Although the data cannot be interpreted unambiguously, the results nevertheless point to a scalable relevance of competencies for R&I collaborations in engineering industries. The fact that *learning* of new content and the ability to *handle complexity* stand out can be understood against this background as confirmation of the hypothesis that professional profiles are becoming increasingly dynamic - as summarized by the term employability in the interplay between person, organization and policy [38]. It is noticeable that *diversity* and *dealing with emotions*, which can also be described as *empathy*, together with *creativity* play a significantly less important role for R&I processes if the self-assessment of industry is to be believed.

3.2 Competencies by Sectors Industry

Looking at industry sectors individually, it becomes apparent that *creativity* is in conspicuously low demand in mechanical engineering. The same applies to *dealing with diversity* in chemical engineering, while *teamwork* on the other hand seems to be

particularly important here. There are hardly any differences between the sectors with regard to the importance of *dealing with complexity* and only minor differences in the importance of *teamwork* and *motivation to learn*. Hence, a cross-sector consensus with regard to the three most relevant competencies exists.

Table 4 - Competencies listed by industry sector (possible max. =1, min. = 5)

Competency	Automotive engineering	Chemical engineering	Electrical engineering	Mechanical engineering
agility	1,68	1,62	1,57	1,63
agency in systems	1,61	1,40	1,48	1,63
handling complexity	1,38	1,34	1,36	1,38
process analysis and design	1,45	1,43	1,31	1,52
teamwork	1,46	1,29	1,40	1,48
attitude towards challenges	1,57	1,67	1,52	1,79
acting according to ethical principles	1,58	1,27	1,56	1,65
agency despite uncertainties and contradictions	1,53	1,39	1,47	1,55
motivation to learn	1,35	1,28	1,28	1,37
critical thinking	1,51	1,35	1,48	1,55
recognizing emotions and taking other perspectives	1,83	1,83	1,82	1,91
reflection of own actions	1,51	1,48	1,34	1,44
handling diversity	1,94	2,37	2,05	2,11
creativity	1,64	1,76	1,70	1,95

The interviewed managers reported that most of the competencies have similar relevance in all considered industry sectors. Analyses of variance (ANOVA) show that the differences in competency values in individual industries are not significant. With *acting according to ethical principles*, there is, however, a single exception.⁴ Considering the descriptive level of mean values, there are notable results of the

⁴ The relevance of the competency *acting according to ethical principles* differs with statistical significance for the four industry sectors: $F(3,174)=4.02$, $p<.01$.

survey. Among these is that *attitude toward challenges* in mechanical engineering is rated by interviewees as comparatively low in relevance, and represents a negative deviation from the mean value. The same applies to *handling diversity* in chemical engineering and *creativity* in mechanical engineering. The latter is particularly noteworthy because the design process, as part of mechanical engineering, would lead one to expect a different level of importance. In addition, there are also positive deviations. For example, managers from chemical engineering state that *acting according to ethical principles* is of particular importance with the best sector-specific value of all, while the other industrial sectors only achieve a medium value.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

The results of the survey support the typology of important competencies for collaborative R&I derived from literature and show that these competencies are in demand in research-oriented industries. However, it was found that R&I managers regard these competencies to be relevant to varying degrees.

Of particular relevance are *motivation to learn* and *handling complexity*. *Motivation to learn* addresses the individual attitude towards acquiring new or deepening existing knowledge, capabilities, or attitudes. The emphasis lies on the willingness to control one's own learning process and to activate necessary resources and engage in adequate social interactions [13,24,25]. *Handling complexity* refers to the ability to recognize and understand relevant interrelations and patterns in situations with an unknown number of different variables and dynamic interactions between these variables, in order to align one's own actions in an impact-oriented manner [14,39].

With the competencies *teamwork* and *process analysis and design*, which are also considered highly relevant, the results support the observation that cross-organizational and cross-sector innovation activities are becoming increasingly important and require new competencies from those involved in order to successfully shape highly dynamic and complex collaboration processes.

The *Wheel of Competencies* can be used to generate distinct competency profiles based on context-specific parameters and individual needs. Thus, the *Wheel of Competencies* can be used to identify and depict the requirements for individual sectors or transfer activities and collaboration formats. By illustrating the requirements in this way, needed qualifications can be addressed in a second step with customized training programs or curricula respectively. This provides opportunities for professional education programs, further and executive education, but likewise for academic higher education.

4.2 Implications

In engineering education, these results help to identify not only subject-specific and disciplinary educational content, but also those competencies that are becoming increasingly important in professional careers and that enable inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration in R&I networks. In this context, competency profiles

can be identified that derive specifically from the perspective of an academic discipline. For example, the relevance of the *ethical dimension* is particularly evident in chemical engineering. This should be reflected in appropriate courses of study and continuing education programs.

On this basis, firstly, curricula can be revised and supplemented with respective content. More importantly, however, this emphasizes the need to focus engineering education on competencies by implementing appropriate teaching and learning methods and didactic concepts that address these competencies. This will not have to come at the expense of the disciplinary content, but can be accomplished as an integrated approach, as I demonstrate elsewhere [40]. However, it requires a mindset change with respect to teaching and learning formats, which are too often designed traditionally in a frontal way and thus forfeit considerable potential. Which teaching and learning methods are suitable cannot be answered in general terms and must be explored in the context of the respective study programs and courses. Generally speaking, however, the focus on competency development can be a means to prepare for both changing job descriptions as well as those jobs that are currently emerging or will emerge in the near future [41]. The competencies studied here refer to underlying dispositions and, hence, are most likely to be understood as transversal competencies, but at the same time they form a foundation for acquiring new and developing existing professional competencies. The results can then also inform professional (further) education. The *Wheel of Competencies* may serve as a tool for the development of tailor-made training programs, enabling providers and recipients of trainings to identify specific focal points and to agree on desired outcomes. The typology of competencies illustrated in the *Wheel of Competencies* does not claim to be complete or exhaustive and can therefore be individually adapted to the requirements in the respective application.

4.3 Limits

The results of the study should be interpreted considering its limitations. First, the competencies considered in the study cannot claim to be exhaustive because collaborations in specific research fields or innovation ecosystems may require different competency profiles. Second, only four industry sectors were surveyed. While the comparison of results across sectors suggests generalizability, it cannot demonstrate it conclusively. Third, despite the sample size of 200 enterprises, it cannot be ruled out that there is a common method bias [42].

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